

Reaction of L-cystine with *cis*-diaqua(ethylenediamine)platinum(II) cation : A kinetic and mechanistic study

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Abstract : Substitution reaction of *cis*-diaqua(ethylenediamine)platinum(II) cation by L-cystine (H_4L^{2+}) has been studied spectrophotometrically over the range $7.5 \leq 10^4 [\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}} \leq 50.0$, $3.04 \leq \text{pH} \leq 4.43$, $40 \leq t \leq 60$ °C and $I = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³ (NaClO_4). The reaction takes place via an outer sphere association between the aquaplatinum(II) cation and H_4L^{2+} followed by transformation of the outer into inner-sphere complex by slow interchange. The anation rate constant at 25 °C and $I = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³ (NaClO_4) is found to be 3.39×10^{-4} s⁻¹, ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger for k_{an} path are found to be 28.9 kJ mol⁻¹ and -214.4 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. The anation reaction at platinum(II) center follows an Ia path.

Keywords : Kinetics and mechanism, platinum(II) cation, L-cystine.

Coordination of platinum(II) compounds to amino acids has been the subject of extensive studies in last two decades owing to the anticancer activities of *cis*-platin and related compounds¹. Due to major toxic effect of *cis*-platin, aqua derivatives are now widely used, as one would expect the aqua species to react much faster² in cell than the dichloro species. In general substitution at platinum(II) center follows an associative mechanism that is characterized by a second order rate law and significantly negative activation volume and entropies³. However, there are some reports where dissociative mechanism^{4,5} has been postulated for the substitution reaction at platinum(II) center. De and coworker¹ have done extensive work on the reaction of $\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{OH}_2)_2^{2+}$ with pyridine-2-thiol, L-glutamine, guanosine, DL-penicillamine, adenosine-5'-monophosphate, glutathione (reduced), L-asparagine and glycylglycine. However the reaction of $\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{OH}_2)_2^{2+}$ with L-cystine (which is an oxidized product of L-cysteine) has not been studied. In order to understand the mechanism of substitution properly the reaction of L-cystine with $\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{OH}_2)_2^{2+}$ is reported.

Results and discussion

In the first set of kinetic experiments, the $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{OH}_2)_2^{2+}]$ was varied at fixed $[\text{Cystine}]_{\text{T}}$ of 15.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. The ionic strength, pH and temperature were kept constant. The pseudo first order plots were linear giving $10^4 k_{\text{obs}} = (2.62 \pm 0.02)$ s⁻¹ and showing

that the reaction is first order in $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{OH}_2)_2^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$ (T = Total). The independence of k_{obs} at 50 °C under the condition $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}} = 15.0 \times 10^{-4}$, $I = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³ and pH = 3.95 over the $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}]_{\text{T}}$ range from 7.68×10^{-5} to 15.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ is in agreement with first order dependence in $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}]_{\text{T}}$. The rate law is therefore given by eq. (1).

$$\text{Rate} = -d[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}]_{\text{T}}/dt = k_{\text{obs}}[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}]_{\text{T}} \quad (1)$$

Effect of variation of $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]$ on the reaction rate :

At a fixed $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}]_{\text{T}} = 7.68 \times 10^{-5}$, $I = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³ and pH = 3.95, the effect of $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$ on the rate of the reaction was studied in 7.5×10^{-4} to 50×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ range at 40, 50, 55, 60 °C. The results are collected in Table 1. The k_{obs} values increase with increase in $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$. The plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$ is curved attaining a limiting value at higher concentration of the entering ligand indicating that the reaction is zero order in $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$ at the limiting region. The observed order is less than unity in $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$ is probably due to outer-sphere association at higher concentration of $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$. A plot of k_{obs}^{-1} vs $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}^{-1}$ is linear.

Effect of varying pH on the rate :

Under the conditions $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}]_{\text{T}} = 7.68 \times 10^{-5}$, $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}] = 7.5 \times 10^{-4}$, $I = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³ (NaClO_4). pH was changed from 3.04 to 4.43. $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (50 °C) values were found to increase from 0.94 to 1.83 s⁻¹. At pH = 3.04,

Table 1. Values of $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1}) at different $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$ and at different temperatures

[Complex A]_T = 7.68×10^{-5} , pH = 3.95, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO₄)

$10^4 [\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$ (mol dm^{-3})	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)			
	40	50	55	60
7.5	1.31	1.51	1.74	2.35
10.0	1.62	1.92	2.24	3.02
15.0	2.10	2.62	3.17	4.22
18.0	2.49	3.02	3.58	4.70
30.0	3.31	4.33	5.14	6.00
50.0	3.89	4.92	6.70	7.46
$10^4 k_{\text{an}}/\text{s}^{-1}$	6.25	9.22	10.60	13.10

K_{os} (average) 3.54 ± 0.80 .

3.52, 3.95, 4.43 the values of $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ are 0.94, 1.01, 1.51 and 1.83 s^{-1} respectively.

Since $\text{p}K_1$ and $\text{p}K_2$ values⁷ for *cis*-diaqua (ethylenediamine)platinum(II) ion are 5.8 and 7.60 respectively, we can assume that at pH=3.90 the Pt^{II} complex exists as diaqua ion. Increasing the pH of the medium the concentration of H_3L^+ , H_2L and HL^- will increase. Under the experimental condition H_4L^{2+} , H_3L^+ and H_2L will be present. However at pH = 3.95, H_2L would be the predominant species. The values of $\text{p}K_1$, $\text{p}K_2$ and $\text{p}K_3$ of L-cysteine⁸ are 1.04, 2.05 and 8.0 respectively.

Increase in k_{obs} with the increase in pH is probably due to increase in the concentration of H_2L , which is stronger nucleophile in comparison to H_3L^+ .

Probable mechanism may be delineated as in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The rate law for anation reaction can be derived in the following manner.

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{an}} [\text{O.S}]_e$$

$$= k_{\text{an}} K_{\text{os}} [\text{Complex A}]_e [\text{H}_2\text{L}]_e \quad (2)$$

$$[\text{Complex A}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{Complex A}]_e + [\text{O.S}]_e \quad (3)$$

$$= [\text{Complex A}]_e + K_{\text{os}} [\text{Complex A}]_e [\text{H}_2\text{L}]_e$$

$$= [\text{Complex A}]_e \{1 + K_{\text{os}} [\text{H}_2\text{L}]_e\}$$

$$[\text{Complex A}]_e = \frac{[\text{Complex A}]_{\text{T}}}{\{1 + K_{\text{os}} [\text{H}_2\text{L}]_e\}} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Complex A}]_{\text{T}} \quad (5)$$

From eqs. (2) and (5)

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{an}} K_{\text{os}} [\text{H}_2\text{L}]_e \{1 + K_{\text{os}} [\text{H}_2\text{L}]_e\} \quad (6)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}}^{-1} = k_{\text{an}}^{-1} + (k_{\text{an}} K_{\text{os}})^{-1} \times [\text{H}_2\text{L}]_e^{-1} \quad (7)$$

The plot of k_{obs}^{-1} vs $[\text{H}_4\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}^{-1}$ should be linear with an intercept = k_{an}^{-1} and slope = $(k_{\text{an}} K_{\text{os}})^{-1}$. This plot is linear at all temperatures studied. k_{an} was determined from the reciprocal of the intercept and K_{os} was calculated from intercept/slope ratio. The value of k_{an} and K_{os} are collected in Table 1.

Effect of temperature on rate :

The reaction was studied at four different temperatures with varying ligand concentrations. Activation parameters were computed using weighted programme of Eyring equation, and the values were compared with literature data of analogous systems (Table 2). The low ΔH^\ddagger values 28.9 kJ mol^{-1} compared with the aqua exchange process⁹ together with highly negative ΔS^\ddagger ($-214.4 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) suggests an associative mechanism.

Table 2. Activation parameters for analogous systems

System	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (JK mol ⁻¹)	Ref.
<i>cis</i> -[Pt(en)(OH ₂) ₂] ²⁺ + H ₂ O*	90.0	-43.0	10
DL-Methionine	15.58 ± 0.9	-230.0 ± 3	11
Thioglycolic acid	29.51 ± 4.8	-188 ± 15	11
Adenosine	63.7 ± 1.6	-58 ± 5	11
Thiourea	61.95 ± 1.3	-71 ± 5.8	11
Thiosemicarbazide	35.69 ± 0.8	-166.0 ± 2.54	11
L-Cystine	28.9	-214.4	This work

The value of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger as 28.9 kJ mol⁻¹ and -214.4 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ are comparable with ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values of the anation reaction between *cis*-[Pt(en)(OH₂)₂]²⁺ with thioglycolic acid¹¹. The low value of $K_{os} = 3.54 \pm 0.8$ is indicative of the fact that the reaction is probably taking place between *cis*-[Pt(en)(OH₂)₂]²⁺ (having two units of positive charges) and H₂L (neutral species).

Experimental

The reactant complex, *cis*-[Pt(en)(OH₂)₂]²⁺ (complex A) was prepared by the published method⁶ and was characterized spectrally⁷ and by elemental analysis. The pH of the solution was so maintained (pH = 3.95) that >90% of the perchlorate salt was obtained as diaqua species. Upon addition of acidic *cis*-[Pt(en)(OH₂)₂]²⁺ solution to a solution of L-cystine an increase in absorbance in the visible range occurred. The absorption spectra of *cis*-[Pt(en)(OH₂)₂]²⁺ and the mixture (L-cystine + *cis*-[Pt(en)(OH₂)₂]²⁺) at the same pH indicates the formation of a platinum(II) complex where L-cystine is bound to Pt^{II} centre. The absorbance increase of the mixture at different time intervals is shown in the Fig. 1. The composition of the product in solution was also determined by modified Job's method⁸ of continuous variation. The metal ligand ratio was found to be 1 : 1. The pH of the solution was adjusted by adding NaOH/HClO₄ and the measurements were carried out with the help of Nucleonix digital pH meter with an accuracy of ±0.01 units. Doubly distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The reactions were carried out at constant ionic strength (0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄).

Kinetic measurements :

Kinetic measurements were carried out spectrophotometrically using a Systronics UV-Vis spectrophotometer

Fig. 1. Repetitive spectral scan of the *cis*-[Pt(en)(OH₂)₂]²⁺ and L-cystine mixture. [Pt^{II}] = 1.0 × 10⁻⁴, [L-cystine] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, pH = 4.40, temp. = 50 °C, (1) Pt^{II} only, (2) mixture at zero time, (3)-(6) at 1, 2, 4, 6.5 h interval respectively.

model 119. The reaction progress was monitored at 240 nm, pseudo first order condition were maintained throughout the runs by using a large (> 10 folds) excess of L-cystine. The rate constant k_{obs} were obtained from the slope of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ vs t plots (eq. (8))

$$\ln(A_\infty - A_t) = k_{obs}.t + C \quad (8)$$

A_t and A_∞ are the absorbances of the reaction at time t and at equilibrium respectively. The reported data represented as an average of duplicate runs were reproducible to within ±3%. The correlation coefficient of plot used to determine k_{obs} was found to be 0.99 in most of the cases.

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References

- (a) P. S. Sengupta and G. S. De, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 928; (b) P. S. Sengupta, R. Sinha and G. S. De, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 509; (c) *Trans Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 638; (d) 2002, **27**, 550; (e) P. S. Sengupta, R. Sinha, S. K. Bera and G. S. De, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 712; (f) S. K. Bera, S. K. Chandra and G. S. De, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2003, **35**, 252; (g) S. K. Bera, P. S. Sengupta and G. S. De, *Inorg. React. Mech.*, 2003, **5**, 65; (h) S. K. Bera and G. S. De, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1882; (i) Rosenberg, L. Van Camp, J. E. Trosko and V. H. Mansur, *Nature*, 1969, **222**, 385; (j) P. Umopathy, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1989, **95**, 129; (k) B. Lippert, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **37**, 1; (l) W. I. Sundquist and S. J. Lippard, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **100**, 293; (m) E. Lempers and L. M. Reedijk, *J. Adv. Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, **37**, 175; (n) J. Reedijk, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1992, **198-200**, 873.

2. N. P. Johnson, J. P. Hoeschele and R. O. Rahn, *Chem. Biol. Interactions*, 1980, **30**, 151.
3. (a) S. Suvachitanont, H. Hohmann, Rudi Van Eldik and J. Reddijk, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **33**, 895; (b) R. Jacobs, F. Prinloo and E. J. Brect, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 212.
4. (a) U. Frey, L. Helm, A. E. Merbach and R. Romco, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **111**, 8161; (b) Biljana V. Petrović and Željadin D. Bugarčić, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 2005, **58**, 544.
5. R. Romeo, A. Grassi and L. M. Scolaro, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 4383.
6. M. C. Lim and R. B. Martin, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 1911.
7. R. F. Coley and D. S. Martin (Jr.), *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1973, **7**, 573.
8. R. D. Cannon, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1981, 1924.
9. "Ullman's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry", Vol. A2, 'Amines, Aliphatic to Antibiotics', VCH, Weinheim (Federal Republic of Germany), 1985, pp. 62-63.
10. M. L. Tobe and J. Burgess, "Inorganic Reaction Mechanism", Longman, London, 1997.
11. S. Ghosh, P. S. Sengupta and G. S. De, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 453.